

Positioning stabilization with reinforcement learning for multi-step robot positioning tasks in Nvidia Omniverse

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Abstract—For many years, universal robots have been extensively popular across a wide range of industries to accommodate a broad range of manufacturing requirements. The complexity of manufacturing environments has resulted in a growing demand for automated programming approaches for robotic systems, where artificial intelligence approaches have recently proven effective. Despite recent advancements, the development of AI-driven controllers for universal robots performing complex, multi-step tasks continues to face several challenges, including stability issues. This paper aims to address these challenges by leveraging reinforcement learning to automate robot programming, with a particular focus on ensuring the stability of robot movements during multi-step robot positioning for inspection purposes. Our research formulates the multi-step robot positioning task as a reinforcement learning problem and develops a reward function to account for the robots’ stability at the checkpoints. We conducted experiments using four different RL methods, namely PPO, TRPO, SAC, and TD3. Our findings indicate that TRPO outperforms the other methods, converging to an optimal controller. This study contributes to the field of robotics by providing a robust approach to enhancing the stability and efficiency of robot programming in complex manufacturing environments.

Index Terms—Stability, multi-step robot positioning, Reinforcement Learning, robotic controller

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the use of universal manipulator robots has increased across numerous industries due to their increased flexibility and reduced costs resulting from mass production. The emergence of fully programmable universal robots has consequently diverted the community’s attention more toward the controller design process than the mechanical configuration. Moreover, in light of the increasing complexity of manufacturing customized products, the controller design problem becomes increasingly complex.

Increasing attention is being paid to intelligent controllers, which integrate artificial intelligence into their design to reduce their engineering challenges.

Recent advances in artificial intelligence algorithms have facilitated the development of automated approaches to developing control systems, especially in robotics. At present, the community seeks to develop control systems capable of automating both high-level and low-level tasks. Researchers have conducted a variety of studies concerning the positioning of robot actuators at a low level.

It should be noted, however, that the positioning task poses a significant challenge when the desired location is reached but

the actuator is required to remain at the point for an extended period of time. In automated controller design, this problem is referred to as stability, especially in cases where the control mechanism requires continuous operation. It is necessary for the controller to learn to keep the sensor in the same position for a sustained period of time without making additional movements. To maintain position, the necessary parameters can be manually set as part of a manual solution. A controller that is automatically programmed will, however, need to learn to maintain this stability and manual disruption during the execution of the controller will interfere with the objectives that depend on the continuous execution of the controller. In specific, in a high-level control mechanism, maintaining the position is only an action or a decision similar to any other decision, for instance, moving with a certain acceleration and speed towards a certain direction. The problem is more challenging with RL where the reward function should be defined in such a manner that could handle combinations of different objectives.

In this research, we present an RL-based approach for designing a robotic controller that is able to maintain a certain level of stability in the context of multi-step robot positioning.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews the relevant literature focusing on the works concerning stability in RL-based controllers. Section 3 describes our methodology. In section 4, we present our experiments and discuss the results. Finally, in section 5, we conclude the research and the results obtained during this research.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A variety of industries, such as manufacturing, logistics and household automation, depend on robotic functional tasks that involve manipulating and moving objects. While traditionally the engineering cycle for designing control mechanisms for robotic systems had to impose difficulties in many aspects to be tackled via complex manual efforts, people are now interested in more automated approaches to optimal and effective robot programming. The introduction of reinforcement learning techniques has provided an automated approach for training robotic systems to perform tasks optimally and reliably. Through RL, robots are able to learn from their interactions with the virtual environment initially, resulting in improved decision-making capabilities over extended training horizon, being able to deal with uncertainty and dynamicity with almost

zero prior knowledge about the working environment. Here are some effective works found in the literature discussing the use of RL for robot programming with focus on universal robots in particular for the pick and place problem.

The concept of stabilization of the movement of the manipulator robot is an integral part of a variety of industrial applications such as in manufacturing, healthcare and service robots. This is more prevalent in tasks such as high-precision welding in an industrial setting, close contact inspection tasks, or automated robot-based surgery in healthcare centers. The study [1] takes a closer look at designing an end effector and presenting a control algorithm that provides a stabilized end effector for the purpose of drilling. Minimal-invasive surgeries also require highly precise control over their end effector especially when dealing with heart surgeries such as in the study provided in [2]. In the past decades various controllers have been suggested for robotic control. This includes control strategies that involve just the position control as well as position and force control-based methods. Proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control [3], adaptive control with Neural networks [4], hybrid position/force control (sensor-based) [5] etc.

Providing stability becomes even more challenging when the control strategy encompasses force control or the problem faces a constraint-specific environment.

In sensitive multi-step robot positioning applications, such as multi-step inspection studied in [6], if the inspection is based on tactile sensors, there is a high risk that an unprecedented move could lead to a task failure. The End-effector positioning stabilization problem involves the ability to maintain the end-effector at a desired location, orientation, or movements on the desired path, which is in practice dealt with in the presence of disturbances, external forces, or uncertainty.

Though we could see a lot of experiments out there that focus on the stability of the manipulator robot with classical control approaches, for reinforcement learning-based approaches, the application is quite different. In [7] the stability of the end-effector is optimized for the movement of the robot from a free motion to a constrained environment using discontinuous transition control algorithms. A perfect example of stability optimization for a hybrid position and force control is provided in [8]. In relation to control strategies using reinforcement learning techniques, the maneuverability with Point to Point control is very limited. In a restricted setting, there would be a need for sudden changes in the acceleration and velocity of the robot when encountered by an obstacle. Most of the time, the way to have a hand on this problem for Reinforcement learning is environment shaping.

Over the years, Deep Reinforcement Learning algorithms have been used to solve a variety of intelligent tasks. The involvement of Reinforcement Learning with robotics broadened the scope of the tasks that a robot could do with

limited time. Interestingly, research on control strategies with Reinforcement learning has also been on the rise. Though the control methods using DQN-based agents prove to be successful with Kuka KR16, a 6 DOF-based robot as in [9], the limitation of exponential increase in dimensionality would be an issue in complex environments. The research focusing on continuous control [10] provides the usage of deep deterministic Policy gradient (DDPG) for controlling a continuous state-space manipulation of soft robotics. The DDPG [11] has an actor and a critic structure that can calculate the goodness of each action taken by the agent in a particular state. Here as well, the curse of dimensionality and overestimation of the Q values can be a significant overhead for the robot control problem. These problems are addressed by the current state of the algorithms such as the Trust Region Policy Optimization (TRPO) [12] and Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [13].

The ability for them to have control over the network updating process limited the problem of overestimation bias. Though the problem of the curse of dimensionality is not directly dealt with, the controlled learning mechanism improved the comprehension of increased state space. Though there are different versions of PPO but improved training methods, the original paper suggested a clipped Surrogate Objective method that measures the improvement of the policy while constraining the policy update. In [14], PPO and SAC have been utilized to address the problem of balancing an Inverted Pendulum mobile manipulator. Considering stability, in [15], a set of state networks, a critic network, and an action network is used to come up with an optimal control policy by optimizing the performance index. The [16] paper provides a different methodology of integrating Reinforcement Learning and classical control methods to provide a more stable controller. Here they employed Reinforcement Learning in the context of a model-based approach where the agent doesn't have to figure out all the details required for controlling the robot. The action space is appropriately designed in a way to allow for the secure learning of a decentralized PD feedback controller to account for uncertainties brought on by model mismatch or outside disruptions. There have also been studies related to single-link flexible manipulators with Reinforcement Learning. The paper published in 2017 [17], has a focus on the suppression of the vibrations due to its flexible nature and its lightweight structure. The incorporation of an actor-critic method in combination with an assumed model method (AMM) [18] truncates the dynamic equations to some finite-dimensional model. The critic in the system is used to approximate the cost function of the system and the actor-network is used to provide a proper control input to the system. According to the author, the combination of reinforcement learning with the Lyapunov stability method provided better stability in comparison to the PD control. The study provided by [19] similar to [17] is based on a flexible two-link manipulator in which an agent based on actor-critic is used to act as a controller that enables vibration suppression

along with trajectory tracking. A simulation was also carried out to test the control approach provided on a discretized ODE dynamic model. Contrasted with the PD controller, this model has proven to be a more effective control method.

As inferred from the review above, it is evident that RL is capable of handling complex stability-based manipulation tasks but all these experiments only focus on the RL agent carrying out a process in a stable manner and not a method where the agent is made to stay consistent in a definite spot for some time. With this study, we focus more on the stability of the manipulator robot called the UR10 [20], during an inspection task having a pin-point stabilization for a specific duration of time.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we will describe how we developed the RL-based controller for providing stability in multi-step robot positioning problems. In this regard, first, a brief description of the problem concerned is provided and then the methodology proposed for establishing stability for multi-step robot positioning using an RL-based controller is described.

When it comes to manipulator robot controller design, logical approaches are generally easier to implement than RL approaches, especially when stability is an issue [21]. The use of logic approaches may prove to be effective in this regard, since once a desired pose has been achieved, the robot can be programmed not to make any additional movements unless they are necessary. In an RL-based approach, stabilizing an agent is challenging since there are no fixed or programmatic methods for fine-tuning the agent's behavior. When RL is used to design a controller for a robotic system, a lack of understanding of the dynamics of a robot can also lead to difficulties in stabilizing it, especially when it comes to positioning [22]. This study uses a base-line RL controller design presented in [6], which addresses the problem of UR10 multi-step positioning in the lack of concern for stability. Therefore, this study will use the base-line controller presented in [6] to propose a solution to stabilization in the context of multi-step robot positioning. This solution will incorporate a mixture of intricate reward functions that encourage the agent to maintain a desired position for a particular period of time.

Specifically, this is required in multi-step positioning operations since the robot must remain in a defined position for another operation to complete or else non-stability would pose a risk to the operation.

Several approaches have already been devised to address the stability of manipulator robots over the years. Stability requirements vary greatly depending on the nature of the task. There can be a difference between the stability requirements for pick-and-place tasks and inspection tasks. An example of an inspection task would be a visual inspection of mechanical parts to detect defects where the camera is attached to the actuator (part of the robot that interacts with the environment). To ensure accurate imaging and reliable defect detection, the camera needs to be positioned at a particular position. Failure to meet these stability conditions may result in image blurring,

inconsistent data acquisition, reduced system performance, and ultimately task failure.

In this study, our primary objective is to build an RL-based intelligent agent to lead a robotic actuator to visit a consecutive set of predetermined inspection points (hereafter check-points) one after another while maintaining stability during inspection operations.

An inspection task is defined in such a way that once the actuator (sensor) reaches a point of inspection, it stays at that point for a period of time until the corresponding inspection task is completed.

As soon as the robot has completed inspection at one checkpoint, the actuator moves to the next checkpoint, and this process is repeated for all specified checkpoints.

RL is an experience-based learning process that involves sequential interactions between agents and their environments. It is therefore necessary to define an observation space that is composed of variables that influence the agent's understanding of the system at the moment.

As a result, the observation provides the agent with a sense of whether the objective has been achieved or implicitly, a measure of how far the agent is from achieving that goal.

Based on [6], the observation space for implementing an RL controller for multi-step robot positioning of a UR10 robotic system relies on the following factors:

- UR10 joint positions
- UR10 joint velocity
- Goal position
- Goal rotation
- Goal relative rotation
- Previous action
- Action moving average
- Tolerance timer

The UR10 robot consists of six joints: the base, shoulder, elbow, wrist-1, wrist-2, and wrist-3. In the observation space, UR10 joint positions can range from -360° to 360° . Fig. 1 provides a visual of the joints along with their maximum joint limits and velocities for a UR10 robot.

Also, the goal rotation represents the rotation of the sensor/actuator at the position of the goal. Goal relative rotation is defined as the difference between the current orientation of the actuator and the desired orientation. Essentially, it represents the change in orientation required in order to align the actuator with the target rotation. However, in this study, we consider the sensor/actuator to work separately in terms of orientation and thus our control equation does not include the sensor's orientation in the controller design process.

The controller's job is, however, the definition of the movement trajectory for the actuator from the current location to the target location. Random fluctuations around the target location, in technical terms instability, is then the aim of the controller in this study to avoid as it will mainly cause damages to the sensor and the object being inspected [23]. As an attempt to address this problem, we suggest the use of a term so-called the action moving average in the control equation, used for smoothing the motion trajectory. This will also account for the

stability and the risks imposed by temporal fluctuation during the transfer phase. Apart from the provided observations, the tolerance timer is an addition to the system. A description of the inclusion of the timer will follow in this section, while briefly the primary objective of the timer is to determine the length of time within which temporal fluctuations should be controlled for the sake of stability.

Name	Joints	
	Max. Joints Limits -/+ [°]	Max. Joints Velocity [°/s]
Base	-360/ 360	120
Shoulder	-360/ 360	120
Elbow	-360/ 360	180
Wrist 1	-360/ 360	180
Wrist 2	-360/ 360	180
Wrist 3	-360/ 360	180

Fig. 1: UR10 Joints with their Max. Joint Limits and Velocities

Since maintaining the actuator position at a checkpoint (in other words stability) is challenging, we introduce a tolerance for the agent to be more flexible in the implementation of stability. In this paper, stability is defined as the ability of a robot to maintain its actuator within a specified radius of its intended location. Consequently, stability is achieved if the distance between the current position of the sensor/actuator and the desired position remains constant for a specified period of time.

As the RL agent observes the environment, it should compare the observation with the desired situation, and then take action accordingly (move the robot to the desired position). There is a concept in RL known as the action space which describes the number of parameters our RL-based controller would modify in order to move toward the desired location. Based on [6], our action space for implementing the multi-step positioning of UR10 is a collection of 7 variables:

- action moving average [0.01 - 0.1]
- Six/6 Joint positions * [-2*pi, 2*pi]

To ensure a controlled movement, the smoothness factor must be calibrated based on the positional relationship between the actuator and the goal position.

With the smoothness factor dynamically adjusted, the path characteristics can be tailored to suit varying distances between the sensor/actuator and the target position, allowing for controlled navigation in close proximity to the target.

The smoothness factor is therefore assigned to the agent as an adaptable parameter for optimization.

The UR10 joint positions are also an important aspect of the action space, as previously discussed in the observation space. Based on the observations received from the environment, the agent may select one of the joint limits shown in Fig. 2. Furthermore, the continuous nature of all actions within the action space ensures fine-grained control of the system.

In an attempt to formulate our robot positioning problem into an RL problem, as discussed in [6], we would be required to move the sensor/actuator towards the desired position via a trajectory of discrete steps. In the context of robot positioning, this problem is known as motion planning. To be more precise, our goal from training the RL agent is to learn how to move the robot from its current location to the desired location via some finite decisions and thus, the continuous space of motion planning is discretized into several steps.

Fig. 2 represents our RL architecture for implementing motion planning in our UR10 robot positioning problem.

Fig. 2: RL controller with Observation and action

After defining the observation and the action space, the last required component for formulating our problem into an RL controller system is the reward function. The RL controller will need to consider two main objectives in the reward function: positioning and stability. Positioning is basically the process at which the distance between the actuator and the target checkpoint is controlled, while stability concerns controlling the amount of vibrations at a given period of time. Therefore, the reward function for the RL controller would require considering *distance factors* with respect to the positioning objectives and *Time factors* for controlling stability.

1) *Time factors*: In this paper, we have incorporated a set of timers in the controller equation as an attempt to maintain the actuator in the vicinity of the target checkpoint during inspection. Among these timers, the tolerance timer T_G plays a vital role. This particular timer records the duration spent by the actuator within the predefined vicinity of the target checkpoint. If by any chance the actuator moves outside the defined proximity, the timer will stop. Even so, the timer will restart once the actuator returns to the specified zone.

Fig. 3 describes in a flowchart the functionality of the timers used to establish stability. The notions used in the flowchart are described as follows:

T_{cube} is a timer that starts counting when a new checkpoint is intended.

T_t is a binary variable signifying whether the actuator is in the defined proximity from the target checkpoint

T_{ideal} is the desired duration within which the actuator should stay continuously in the defined vicinity of the target checkpoint

T_g is a timer that starts counting with T_{cube} and resets when T_t is false and $T_{cube} > 6sec$. In other words, T_g resets when, here, 6 seconds have passed since a new checkpoint is intended but the actuator has not reached the target checkpoint

(within the defined proximity)

T_F is a binary variable indicating whether $T_g == T_{ideal}$

Fig. 3: Functionality of the timers used to establish stability

As shown in Fig. 3, at the start, once a new checkpoint is intended, the timers T_g and T_{cube} will start counting. The following checks are performed at each time step: First, a verification is made to check if T_{cube} is less than 6 seconds. This ensures better clarity on updating T_g pertaining to T_{cube} which is capped at 10 seconds. Once the check is passed (T_g resets for the contrary), a verification for T_t determining the position of the actuator in the vicinity of the goal position is made. Once again T_g resets if the actuator fails to reach to checkpoint within the defined vicinity while begins inspecting if T_{ideal} has been met (the actuator remained stable over the desired period of time). If T_{ideal} is equal to T_g , T_F is set to be true. Here, T_F also represents the local success and is used to reward the agent appropriately.

2) **Distance factors:** The goal distance is the factor used by the agent to estimate how far the actuator is from the target checkpoint. In the 3D coordinate space, this distance is defined using the L2 norm defined as follows:

$$(G_d) = |p_2 - p_1| = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2}$$

The goal position for the actuator has a lifetime of a certain period, once it has appeared in the environment; after which, a new goal position is intended.

In our approach, the success of the attempt will depend on **Local Success** and **Global Success**. An attempt is called locally successful when the T_{ideal} is achieved. An attempt

is called globally successful when the agent achieves T_{ideal} for the entire set of check points continuously and thus the task is completed successfully.

3) **reward Structure:** The reward for the agent is a mix of sparse and dense rewards. The dense rewards are aimed at driving the agent towards the goal position and the sparse rewards focus more on the stabilization. To facilitate broader applicability and maintain abstraction within our experimental setting, we define a set of weights assigned to the reward components in the reward equation: R_s for values between 1 and 10, R_m for values between 10 and 80, and R_l for values greater than 100. Let G_d denote the distance between the actuator and the target checkpoint and G_i represents the value of 0.05 signifying the tolerance limit. The following individual rewards constitute the overall reward to the agent: The reward function is comprised of the following components:

Distance reward (D_r)

D_r is the main reward component that drives the agent towards the goal point. The negative scaling factor gives the agent an estimate of how far the sensor/actuator is from the goal point intended to minimize the overall distance.

$$D_r = G_d * (-R_s) \quad (1)$$

Action penalty (P_r):

For the movement of the robot to be controlled, an action penalty is considered which is calculated by:

$$P_r = \sqrt{\sum_{a=1}^n a_n^2 * P_f} \quad (2)$$

Here, P_f is a negative factor multiplied by the root of the summation of the squares of each action.

Smoothness reward (S_r):

The smoothness reward is a sparse reward and is mostly perceived by the agent when the actuator has reached the defined vicinity from the target checkpoint. The agent is rewarded when the smoothness is the highest at the goal vicinity and no reward, otherwise.

$$S_r = \begin{cases} R_s & , \text{ when } G_d < G_i \text{ and } s < 0.008 \\ 0 & \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Tolerance time reward (T_r):

The tolerance time reward is given to the agent, every time the tolerance time is greater than 0.

$$T_r = \begin{cases} R_m & , \text{ when } T_g > 0sec \\ 0 & \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Local success reward (L_r):

Every time a local success is achieved, the agent is rewarded with a local reward motivating the agent further to finish the

local task as quickly as possible. Otherwise, when a local success is not achieved, a negative reward is assigned to prevent the actuator from increasing distance from the target checkpoint.

$$T_r = \begin{cases} R_l & , \text{ when success} == 1 \\ -R_m & \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Stable action reward (A_s) :

This reward concentrates on rewarding the agent for outputting the same actions on consecutive time steps when the actuator is in the desired vicinity of the checkpoint. In simpler terms, if the tool is in the desired vicinity, to avoid unwanted movements, the agent is given a positive reward for maintaining the same position.

$$A_s = \begin{cases} R_m & , \text{ when } G_d < G_i \text{ and } A_{cur} == A_{prev} \\ 0 & \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Total reward (R) :

The overall reward for the agent is then calculated by:

$$R = D_r + A_s + S_r + T_r + L_r + P_r \quad (7)$$

IV. EVALUATION

A. Problem environment

The experiments are conducted using a simulation environment known as Isaac Sim which is capable of real-time rendering. An advantage of this environment is the incorporation of realistic physics, which facilitates the translation of the design and experimentation implemented in the simulation to the real world. The UR10 was selected for this experiment due to its significant popularity among manufacturers.

The RL functionalities required for training and testing various agents are provided by the SKRL framework [24]. In the RL environment, the process is divided into episodes with definite timesteps.

B. Experimental Setup

The experiment begins with the UR10 and inspection engine positioned on an inspection panel at their default positions. The initial goal point around the engine for the actuator to reach is also generated during the environment initiation phase. Using the reward structure presented in the previous section, the agent drives itself to reach its goal position over time steps. An experiment is deemed ended when the total number of time steps exceeds 1000 or the goal of visiting 6 points has been achieved.

The workflow of the experiment focused primarily on varying time-based parameters. The agent's response to the ideal time the actuator must spend near the goal position was examined. The testing range for ideal time was from 3 to 5 seconds. The agent's response to the change in the ideal

operation duration significantly impacts the overall completion time of the inspection and serves as a way to examine the agent's limits.

Additional functionality and metrics that focus more on the stability of the actuator at the specified goal point are also included. The reward function values are assigned deliberately and strategically, based on priority-based incremental steps to ensure optimal allocation. The RL agent is the controller that provides the joint positions for the robot.

C. Experimental Results

In this study, four RL methods have been used to formulate the problem of stability in multi-step robot positioning. The results for the assessment of the performance of the RL algorithms used are presented via the reward values, accuracy and rejection rate.

- 1) *Accuracy* is a measurement of the distance of the actuator from the goal point. It is configured such that if the distance is 0m, the accuracy is 100 percent, and if the distance is beyond the success tolerance, the accuracy is 0 percent.
- 2) *Rejection Rate*: The ratio of the attempts that failed to be successful but reached all 6 points in less than 70 seconds.

All the experiments conducted are limited to last in training for 100k time-steps, before which convergence for the RL algorithm should be achieved. Convergence, means the RL algorithm has learned to provide a certain level of accuracy and a certain ratio of job rejection. An indication of convergence is the saturation of reward, accuracy or job rejection rate at some certain value. In order to be considered successful, all three measures mentioned above must be saturated, with rewards and accuracy in high values and job rejection rates in low values.

The assessment of the results for the controller trained by PPO is presented in Fig. 4. The results show that PPO According to the results for PPO, the RL controller has saturated in reward and accuracy, but has not been able to lower the rejection rate close to zero in 100k training steps. The fact that PPO's rejection rate is not negligible, despite the fact that reward and accuracy have saturated, concludes that PPO has failed.

Fig 5 shows the results for the controller trained by TRPO.

The results obtained from the TRPO controller indicate that TRPO has provided the required accuracy and also kept the rejection rate at a very low level. Clearly, TRPO has surprisingly outperformed PPO with showing low job rejection rate, at which PPO was a failure.

The results of the controller trained by SAC and TD3 are presented in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, respectively.

The results for SAC and TD3 indicate that neither has been able to demonstrate accuracy nor low rejection rates. Comparison of the results shows TRPO achieved a much lower rejection percentage than the other approaches. The results also indicate that SAC and TD3 have had no success in learning to avoid job rejection in the training phase, as all the jobs are

Fig. 4: The training phase for PPO

Fig. 6: The training results for SAC

Fig. 5: The training results for TRPO

Fig. 7: The training results for TD3

rejected (job rejection rate stays at 1 or 100%) during training. On the other hand, PPO learns during training to lower job rejection rate at some point, while it's deteriorated again near to the end of the training phase.

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VI. CONCLUSION

This research investigated the use of reinforcement learning for the development of a controller for establishing stability in the task of multi-step robot positioning. The proposed method presents a reward equation that accounts for the motion planing problem while incorporating additional components to ensure stability in multi-step inspection tasks. The experiments were conducted in NVIDIA Omniverse using the robotic system named UR10, where four different RL methods were analyzed for developing the RL controller, namely PPO, TRPO, SAC, and TD3. The results of the study showed that TRPO was the only method that could maintain high accuracy while maintaining a low job rejection rate.

REFERENCES

- [1] Zhang, L. and Wang, X., "Dynamic control of a flexible drilling robot end-effector," in *2012 24th Chinese Control and Decision Conference (CCDC)*, 2012, pp. 2199–2204.
- [2] Ishikawa, N. and Watanabe, G., "Robot-assisted cardiac surgery," *Annals of Thoracic and Cardiovascular Surgery*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 322–328, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5761/atcs.ra.15-00145>
- [3] Li, X. and Yu, W., "A systematic tuning method of PID controller for robot manipulators," in *2011 9th IEEE International Conference on Control and Automation (ICCA)*. IEEE, Dec. 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/icca.2011.6138081>
- [4] Gao, Y., Er, M. J., and Yang, S., "Adaptive control of robot manipulators using fuzzy neural networks," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 1274–1278, 2001. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/41.969410>
- [5] Xiao, D., Ghosh, B., Xi, N., and Tam, T., "Sensor-based hybrid position/force control of a robot manipulator in an uncalibrated environment," *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 635–645, Jul. 2000. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/87.852909>
- [6] Bahrpeyma, F., Sunilkumar, A., and Reichelt, D., "Application of reinforcement learning to ur10 positioning for prioritized multi-step inspection in nvidia omniverse," in *2023 IEEE Symposium on Industrial Electronics & Applications (ISIEA)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [7] Pagilla, P. and Yu, B., "A stable transition controller for constrained robots," *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 65–74, Mar. 2001. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/3516.914393>
- [8] Cheah, C., Kawamura, S., and Arimoto, S., "Stability of hybrid position and force control for robotic manipulator with kinematics and dynamics uncertainties," *Automatica*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 847–855, May 2003. [Online]. Available: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0005-1098\(03\)00002-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0005-1098(03)00002-5)
- [9] Cotrim, L. P., José, M. M., and Cabral, E. L. L., "Reinforcement learning control of robot manipulator," *Revista Brasileira de Computação Aplicada*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 42–53, Oct. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5335/rbca.v13i3.12091>
- [10] Li, Y., Wang, X., and Kwok, K.-W., "Towards adaptive continuous control of soft robotic manipulator using reinforcement learning," in *2022 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, Oct. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/iros47612.2022.9981335>
- [11] Lillicrap, T. P., Hunt, J. J., Pritzel, A., Heess, N., Erez, T., Tassa, Y., Silver, D., and Wierstra, D., "Continuous control with deep reinforcement learning," 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1509.02971>
- [12] Schulman, J., Wolski, F., Dhariwal, P., Radford, A., and Klimov, O., "Proximal policy optimization algorithms," 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1707.06347>
- [13] Schulman, J., Levine, S., Moritz, P., Jordan, M. I., and Abbeel, P., "Trust region policy optimization," 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1502.05477>
- [14] Vatsal, V. and Purushothaman, B., "Reinforcement learning of whole-body control strategies to balance a dynamically stable mobile manipulator," in *2021 Seventh Indian Control Conference (ICC)*. IEEE, Dec. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/icc54714.2021.9703140>
- [15] Hu, Y. and Si, B., "A reinforcement learning neural network for robotic manipulator control," *Neural Computation*, vol. 30, no. 7, pp. 1983–2004, Jul. 2018. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1162/neco_a_01079
- [16] Friedrich, S. R. and Buss, M., "A robust stability approach to robot reinforcement learning based on a parameterization of stabilizing controllers," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, May 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/icra.2017.7989382>
- [17] Ouyang, Y., He, W., and Li, X., "Reinforcement learning control of a single-link flexible robotic manipulator," *IET Control Theory Applications*, vol. 11, no. 9, pp. 1426–1433, Jun. 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-cta.2016.1540>
- [18] Korayem, M. H., Rahimi, H., and Nikoobin, A., "Mathematical modeling and trajectory planning of mobile manipulators with flexible links and joints," *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 36, no. 7, pp. 3229–3244, Jul. 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2011.10.002>
- [19] Perrusquía, A., Yu, W., and Soria, A., "Position/force control of robot manipulators using reinforcement learning," *Industrial Robot: the international journal of robotics research and application*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 267–280, Mar. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1108/ir-10-2018-0209>
- [20] Copot, C., Muresan, C., Ionescu, C.-M., Vanlanduit, S., and Keyser, R. D., "Calibration of UR10 robot controller through simple auto-tuning approach," *Robotics*, vol. 7, no. 3, p. 35, Jul. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/robotics7030035>
- [21] Elguea-Aguinaco, Í., Serrano-Muñoz, A., Chrysostomou, D., Inziarte-Hidalgo, I., Bøgh, S., and Arana-Arexolaleiba, N., "A review on reinforcement learning for contact-rich robotic manipulation tasks," *Robot. Comput. Integr. Manuf.*, vol. 81, no. 102517, p. 102517, Jun. 2023.
- [22] Khader, S. A., Yin, H., Falco, P., and Kragic, D., "Learning stable normalizing-flow control for robotic manipulation," in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, May 2021.
- [23] Zhao, R. and Sidobre, D., "Trajectory smoothing using jerk bounded shortcuts for service manipulator robots," in *2015 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, Sep. 2015.
- [24] Serrano-Muñoz, A., Chrysostomou, D., Bøgh, S., and Arana-Arexolaleiba, N., "skrl: Modular and flexible library for reinforcement learning," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 24, no. 254, pp. 1–9, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://jmlr.org/papers/v24/23-0112.html>